

Integrating indigenous and local knowledge into fisheries policy for equitable and sustainable livelihoods

Policy brief

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This policy brief highlights the gendered socio-economic impacts perceived among fisherfolk arising from the implementation of conservation policies to rebuild depleting fish stocks, with a specific focus on Ghana's fishing closed season. It draws attention to fisherfolk's historical observance of micro-closures that support ecological regeneration and identifies the potential synergies between these practices and scientific knowledge. It highlights that fisherfolk get time to rest, repair their fishing gear, and attend to other social obligations. However, the cessation of income from their fishery-related livelihoods has rippling, adverse gendered effects on children's school attendance, household food security, the proliferation of social vices in the community, and the undermining of traditional governance systems. It reveals how the closed season economically displaces fisherfolk, pushing them towards galamsey. This shift not only exacerbates environmental degradation but also fuels social vices that jeopardise community and national security. The findings also underscore that fisherfolk who earn supplementary income from other ventures are more resilient to economic shocks, hence offering a prospective pathway towards a sustainable livelihood plan. Importantly, these research findings have been validated by contributing communities, relevant authorities and stakeholders, as a reflection of fisherfolk's realities. Looking ahead, there is a critical need to recognise indigenous and local knowledge in the fisheries laws for inclusive and equitable resource stewardship.

"The closed season is not a bad idea, but it would have been better in the month of June instead of July to align with the natural period the sea closes itself."

SAVING COLLAPSING FISH STOCKS TO AVERT A LIVELIHOOD CRISIS

The fisheries sector is the backbone of food and livelihood security for more than 10% of Ghana's coastal populations, an estimated 3.5 million people [1]. The sector contributes between 2.6 to 5% of the agricultural GDP and generates an annual foreign exchange of over US\$ 1 billion [2]. Ghana relies heavily on fish as a food source, providing macro- and micronutrients for healthy development. Fish constitutes about 60% of Ghanaians' animal protein intake. The annual per capita consumption of fish in Ghana is 25kg per person per year, higher than the African and global estimates of 10.5kg and 18.9kg, respectively [3]. Following global frameworks such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Ghana's fisheries are key to reducing hunger (SDG 2), reducing poverty (SDG 1), promoting wellbeing (SDG 3), advancing gender equality and reducing inequalities (SDG 5, 10), among other goals.

The pivotal role of fisheries in Ghana is at stake because the small pelagic fisheries, a major species of economic importance, is on the brink of collapse. Small pelagic species, including sardinella, anchovies, and mackerels, are among the most popular and affordable sources of animal protein, thus earning them the description, "the people's fish" [4], [5]. In response to this precarious state of Ghana's fish stocks, scientists, CSOs, and other fisheries stakeholders urged action to rebuild the stocks and avert a looming food and livelihood security crisis for the millions depending on the sector [6], [7]. The Government of Ghana, thus drawing on global practices for addressing depleting fisheries, among other management actions, adopted the fishing closed

season, which has been applied in countries like the Philippines [8], Morocco [9] to ensure sustainability by temporarily prohibiting the harvest of the species during vulnerable periods, such as spawning or migration.

The closed season policy was first introduced for the industrial trawl sector in 2016 and extended to the artisanal fleet in 2019 after strong opposition from fishers in 2018 due to the date. It was subsequently observed for 5 years from 2021 to 2024, except for suspensions in 2020 and 2025. The Creating Synergies between Indigenous Practices and Scientific Knowledge (ISIPSK) research project, aka Sankofa project, investigates the equity and sustainability of conservation policy. Using Ghana's closed season as a case study, its threefold research objectives are to:

- advance knowledge on the perceived gendered socio-economic impacts of implementing the fishing closed season.
- explore the integration of historical indigenous practices beneficial for conservation with scientific knowledge
- share findings to contribute to an effective sub-regional fisheries conservation and sustainable livelihood plan

This policy brief presents key findings from engagements with 833 fisherfolk in 8 major fishing communities (15 landing beaches) across Ghana's four coastal regions during the annual closed season in July 2024 (see Table 1).

FISHERFOLK'S REPORT: STATE OF THE FISHERIES

- 90% of fisherfolk surveyed in all four coastal regions reported that the quantity of fish landed in the past decade had reduced (see Figure 1). They attributed the decline to the destructive operations of industrial trawl vessels that dump juvenile fish they harvest at sea. As small-scale fisherfolk, they acknowledged an increase in the number of canoes, the widespread use of illegal and unsustainable fishing techniques (such as fishing with light, chemicals, and/or small-mesh nets), and the cessation of the observance of traditional rituals, among others.
- 82% of surveyed fisherfolk agreed that action needs to be taken to address the declining fish stocks (see Figure 2). Nonetheless, only 26% of the surveyed fisherfolk share the view that a
- fishing closed season implemented in July was effective in rebuilding depleted resources.
- Fishermen opined that the closed season is counterproductive because the one-month break compels them to disregard the traditional fishing holidays to intensify their fishing efforts, for which they employ illegal methods to guarantee a catch.
"We are forced to go fishing even when the sea is rough to prepare for the closed season. After July, we need to catch more fish to pay our debts" – Crew fisher in Central Region
- Fisherfolk expressed reservations about July for a closed season, as advised by the Scientific Technical Working Group (STWG) to be the spawning period for small pelagic species [11].

Figure 1: Fisherfolk’s observation of fish catches in the past 15 years (which includes the 5 years of implementing a fishing closed season)

Figure 2: Fisherfolk’s response to the question “Is there a need to conserve the fisheries?”

GENDERED SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF THE CLOSED SEASON IN FISHERIES

- As all fishing activities are halted during the closed season, it largely afforded fisherfolk a chance to take a break from their arduous livelihood activities to either maintain their fishing equipment, fish smoking ovens, rest, or attend to social obligations.
- The closed season resulted in a cessation of income, which translated to economic hardships. This was particularly pronounced among male and female fisherfolk without a supplementary source of income. 70% of fisherfolk relied on their fisheries livelihood as their primary and often only source of income (See Figure 3). Due to the unavailability of fresh

- marine fish catches to sustain their livelihoods, there was a reduction, and in most cases, a total halt in the affiliated economic activities throughout the value chain.
- A striking observation among fisherfolk demographic show persons aged 65 and over engaged in fishing longer than ideal for their physiological well-being (see Figure 4).
- Fisheries occupations are gendered. Men predominantly engaged in fishing expeditions and dominated services such as mechanics, hustlers¹ and transporters. Women dominated post-harvest and value-addition activities as fish processors and/or traders, rendering services as food vendors and head porters. Males and females alike own, manage canoes and sell fishing nets among other inputs.
- Perceived impacts were gendered in participants, of which two-thirds were male and one-third female. Male and female fisherfolk experienced similar impacts on their livelihoods; however, women reported a greater burden of domestic responsibilities than men. Women in all four regions reported the undue burden of responsibility placed on them during the closed season. Due to the closure, crew fishers and hustlers were unable to support their families financially or provide fish for food; hence, their wives or female partners bore this responsibility.
- Fisherfolk's large household sizes illustrate their perceived impacts. The average household size ranged between 6 to 10 persons per household. Often, canoe owners or fish mummies who take responsibility for their crew or workers have households of up to 37 people.
- The cessation of fisherfolk's income during the closed season had a ripple effect on their households. The limited access to fresh fish for food affected the quality and quantity of their household meals. Many resorted to buying eggs or frozen meat products, such as chicken or imported fish, from cold stores, which they opined were low in quality and taste due to prolonged freezer storage. Children's attendance at school was negatively affected in 60% participants' households.
- Not all fisherfolk experienced adverse impacts. In Tema, a group of women fresh fish traders disclosed during the focus group discussion that they stored some of the fish landed prior to the closed season in freezers to continue serving their clients during the closed season. *"Since we experience some flow of cash during the closure, we are not adversely impacted by it."* Similarly, a male canoe owner in the Volta region during a key informant interview noted that, *"besides fishing, my wife and I operate other forms of businesses like car transport, community cold store and wood shop. As a result, we do not feel adverse impacts during the closure because our streams of income are diversified"*.
- To cope with their circumstances, popular adaptations included relying on savings from one's livelihood, borrowing money or obtaining loans was the topmost strategy. A male canoe

¹ Persons who engage in various menial jobs at the beach, including carrying fish from the canoes, guarding the canoes at night, among other small jobs.

- owner in the Central region shared, *"I relied on my annual contributions from participating in the VSLA as funds during the closed season"*. Some travelled out of their fishing community for holidays, while others went elsewhere to look for jobs. Fisherfolk engaged in Sekondi and Abuesi (Western Region), reported that youth fisherfolk in their community travelled to Tarkwa and other galamsey2 operational areas to work.
- Several of those in this category were reported to have returned with illness and some died.
- The rate of crime increased during the closed season - theft, burglary, fraud and gambling were the commonest vices.
- The 'Ali' or 'Ahyekon' gear, designed to harvest small pelagic species has become redundant. since they are used mostly in July.

Figure 3: Fisherfolk's response when asked if they had an alternative or supplementary income-generating venture besides their fishery-related venture.

Figure 4: Age of surveyed fisherfolk who research participants in the four coastal Regions

Table 1: Weekly non-fishing days, traditionally observed in the research communities

Region	Fishing Communities	Weekly Fishing Holiday
Volta Region	Abeliakope	Wednesday
	Abutiakope	Wednesday (Sunday*)
Greater Accra Region	Akplabanya	Tuesday (Sunday*)
	Tema	Tuesday (Sunday*)
Central Region	Apam (includes Mumford)	Tuesday (Sunday*)
	Cape Coast (Ekon, Abrofo Mpoano, Ola, Duakor)	Tuesday
Western Region	Sekondi	Tuesday
	Abuesi (includes Kesewokan)	Tuesday (Sunday*)

SOME TRADITIONAL PRACTICES THAT COMPARE WITH SCIENTIFIC CONSERVATION APPROACHES

- It was clear that the practice of observing breaks from fishing was not new to fisherfolk. In all four coastal regions, fishers voluntarily took breaks from fishing in May and June due to what they described as 'natural closed season' resulting from stormy weather at sea.
- Fisherfolk in all eight major research communities historically observed a ban from fishing as part of rituals of festival celebration or in obeisance to their deities, e.g., Nudedefu in the Volta Region, Homowo in Tema, Wichi in Akplabanya, Apitsi in the Central and Western

* Voluntarily observed as a fishing holiday to participate in community events or religious obligations

Regions. These practices are no longer observed in several locations; however, the Tema fisherfolk have upheld their traditional ban on fishing during Homowo festival celebrations.

- Fisherfolk observed weekly non-fishing days or fishing holidays as rest days from fishing, enforced by the respective Chief Fishermen.
- In the Volta region, the forefathers historically performed a ritual known as Nudedefu where an animal is placed into the sea as a sacrifice to the sea deities as a way of reciprocating care to them. This is often

followed by a short ban on fishing. Due to natural processes of decomposition, the carcass attracts smaller marine organisms, including fish. Fisherfolk, however, believed the bumper catches that followed the ritual were the deities' reciprocal benevolence to them.

- Women fish processors and traders employed generational knowledge and skills to design fish smoking ovens that helped them process fish in a way that prolonged the storage span of the fish to reduce post-harvest losses.

CONCLUSIONS

- **Gendered impact:** This research identifies that while the closed season has the benefit of giving fishers time to rest, it halts income from their primary livelihoods. This results in adverse socio-economic impacts with a rippling effect on their households and increases social vices in the community. It confirms the gendered impacts on fisherfolk, with women shouldering a disproportionate burden of family responsibilities compared to men, constraining their economic participation and reinforcing structural gender inequality. Knowledge of the gendered impacts of the policy helps inform equitable outcomes of future policies.
- **Synergies between historical traditional practices and scientific knowledge:** historically, fisherfolk observe weekly fishing holidays and fishing bans as part of traditional rituals which function as micro-closures for ecological regeneration. They were maintained by the traditional governance structures i.e. enforced by the Chief fishermen and other traditional leaders, with the backing of the community's Chief.
- **Sustainable livelihood plan:** Fisherfolk who engaged in supplementary and/or alternative livelihoods were more resilient to the economic shocks due to the limited income to their fishery-related livelihoods.

SANKOFA RECOMMENDATIONS: LEARNING FROM HISTORICAL AND LOCAL ECOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE TO INFORM FUTURE OUTCOMES

- Based on fisherfolk's ecological knowledge, they recommend that the closed season should be implemented (if at all) to align with the natural closure in May/June, which has historically been observed by fisherfolk. Observing a fishing break in May or June mitigates fishers' exposure to unsafe conditions at sea, as these months are characterised by harsh weather and rough sea state.
- The implementation of the fishing closed season could draw upon traditional governance systems that were effective in their applications. This could be accomplished by recognising fisherfolk's traditional authorities and systems through the provisions of Section 169 (1) of the Fisheries Act, 2025 (Act 1146). This call underscores recommendations in the Fisheries Co-Management Policy (2020) and the Gender Mainstreaming Strategy (2016) that advocate for governance arrangements that "combine local knowledge with scientific and technical knowledge of government agencies".
- Introduction of livelihood support programs to provide welfare for fisherfolk 65 years and above, particularly during the closed season.
- The closed season could be complemented with enforcement measures against illegal fishing to increase its effectiveness for rebuilding the fisheries.
- The consequences of sidelining local knowledge and ecological concerns have the potential to cause tension, leading to social, political and ecological implications.

"In the spirit of Sankofa, let us return to the practices and wisdom that have sustained our oceans, and carry them forward into law"

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Disclaimer

This document is co-produced by Dr Ifesinachi Okafor-Yarwood and Josephine Laryea Asare, with contributions from research team members, Kenneth Arthur, Randolph Kwesi Johnson, Isaac Nana Kweigyah, Gabriel Mevuta and Emmanuel Tenkorang. The contents of this report are drawn from fisherfolk perspectives gathered during research fieldwork. While it reflects fisherfolk's lived experiences, the opinions and interpretations contained herein are those of the Sankofa Project team and do not represent the official policies of the University of St. Andrews, the PEW Charitable Trusts or cooperating organisations.

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SANKOFA

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